

Customer Experience Management and Behavioral Intentions in Hotel among Local Tourist

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ABSTRACT: Customer Experience Management has been a critical factor in attracting and retaining customers with a positive guest experience, which leads to repeat business and positive reviews. It includes many different aspects that contribute to overall customer satisfaction. This research sought to identify the factors influencing customer experience management and behavioral intention in hotels among local tourists in Davao City. The study's primary objective is to assess the level of the destination facilities, accommodation services, and incoming travel agencies that can affect customer behavioral intention in hotels in Davao City. The descriptive method was utilized in this study using an adapted, modified questionnaire. The study included a total of 400 respondents. The result showed that most local tourists have a positive response to the hotel's independent factors and behavioral intention in a hotel in Davao City. The findings of the research indicate that accommodation services are at the highest level among local tourists. The researcher's advice is to maintain the highest level of accommodation services in all areas, which indicates cleanliness of the hotel, hospitable staff, safety of the hotel, food quality, and service quality. This implementation will have a positive impact on potential returning customers. Future researchers intend to conduct related research and may use this study as a reference as their guide.

Keywords: *customer experience management, behavioral intention, local tourist*

I. INTRODUCTION

Tourists' behavioral intention is essential in determining their preference for return visits and favorable recommendations from others. A study by Afshardoost and Eshaghi (2020) found that "tourist behavioral intention is a crucial factor in determining tourist behavior, and it is influenced by various factors such as satisfaction, perceived value, and image." However, understanding the determinants of tourist behavioral intention is complex and multi-faceted. According to Özkan, Süer, Keser, and Kocakoç (2020) found that "the relationship between tourist satisfaction and behavioral intention is not straightforward and is influenced by mediating variables such as perceived value, trust, and image." This finding emphasizes the need for a more nuanced understanding of the factors that influence tourist behavioral intention, and the role that these factors play in shaping tourist behavior and outcomes.

Generally, the importance of understanding and influencing tourist behavioral intention cannot be overstated, as it is a crucial factor in encouraging multiple visits, and that is beneficial referrals from friends and Family both of which are essential to the long-term viability of tourist destinations. Thus, the academic literature has extensively acknowledged the significance of Customer Experience Management (CEM) in the contemporary business environment has been extensively acknowledged in the academic literature. A study by Kim (2020) emphasized the role of customer experience in creating customer loyalty and attracting repeat business, stating that "a positive experience with a brand can create trust among consumers and lead to further purchases and excellent referrals." It highlights the importance of the customer experience in fostering customer attachment and luring new clients. Nevertheless, delivering consistent and high-quality experiences to customers remains a challenge for many businesses. Despite this, a survey by Walker (2019) showed that only 8% of companies consider themselves to be customer experience leaders, while most companies need to deliver the level of customer experience that their customers expect. This highlights the need for businesses to better understand the factors that contribute to customer experience and to invest in improving their CEM practices.

Several studies have examined the relationship between customer experience management (CEM) and travelers' behavioral intentions. A study by Cem et al. (2019) found that CEM practices, such as providing high-quality experiences

and personalized service, can result in higher tourist satisfaction levels. The study concluded that "CEM practices have a positive effect on tourist satisfaction, which in turn has a positive impact on tourist behavioral intention." A further study by Rather and Hollebeek (2021) found that "the relationship between customer satisfaction and behavioral intention is strengthened by the presence of positive affective and cognitive responses to the experience." It highlights the importance of delivering high-quality experiences and creating positive emotional connections with customers.

The investigations show how crucial CEM is in influencing travelers' intended behaviors. It is imperative for destinations to prioritize the long-term sustainability of their business by investing in CEM practices, which can enhance the customer experience and raise the probability of repeat business and positive word-of-mouth referrals (Gómez-Suárez & Yagüe, 2021). This study also closes the gap by determining the degree of customer experience management among domestic visitors in Davao City and by developing and articulating a more profound knowledge of the antecedents of trust that influence customer behavioral intention.

This study seeks to determine the level of customer experience management among local tourists regarding destination facilities, accommodation services, and inbound travel agency services, all of which can affect customer behavioral intention to stay in multi-used hotels. To determine the level of behavioral intention perceived among local tourists. To determine the relationships between customer experience management and behavioral intention.

II. Customer Experience Management

In recent years, there have been numerous studies published in the field of Customer Experience Management (CEM), exploring its impact on customer loyalty, satisfaction, and business outcomes. In this section, we will review some of the key studies and authors in the field of CEM. One of the critical studies in the field of CEM was conducted by Jaakko Aspara and Mikko Rönkkö and published in the Journal of Business Research in 2010. In their study, Aspara and Rönkkö investigated, as cited by Iglesias, Markovic, and Rialp (2019), the role of customer experience in creating customer loyalty. They found that positive experiences with a brand were positively associated with customer loyalty.

Another major study in the field of CEM was conducted. It explored the impact of employee behavior on customer satisfaction and found that employees who provided high-quality service were positively associated with customer satisfaction. In a study published in the Journal of Marketing in 2021, Chen, Mandler, & Meyer-Waarden (2021) investigated the impact of personalized experiences on customer loyalty. They found that customers who received personalized experiences were more likely to have higher levels of loyalty to a brand and that they were also more likely to make repeat purchases. Hansen and Laugesen also found that customers valued personalized experiences and that they were willing to pay a premium for these experiences. In a study published in the Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Research in 2018, Chen and Rahman (2018) explored the impact of customer experience on destination loyalty. They found that positive customer experiences were positively associated with destination loyalty and that customers were more likely to return to a destination when they had positive experiences with local businesses and attractions. They also found that customer experiences were essential in shaping customers' perceptions of a destination.

Finally, a study published in the Journal of Service Management in 2020 by de Oliveira et.al. (2020) explored the role of social media in CEM. They found that social media was an important channel for customers to share their experiences with brands and that these experiences had a significant impact on the reputation and image of the brand. They also found that businesses could use social media to enhance the customer experience by providing personalized and responsive customer service and collecting customer feedback and insights.

III. Behavioral Intention

The behavioral intention was referred to as customers who intended to stay in the budget hotel (Manirochana, 2021). In marketing and customer behavior studies, personality was a predominant angle that influenced customer responses, post-purchase behavior, loyalty, and satisfaction (Bukhari, Woodside, Hassan, Shaikh, A. L., Hussain, S., & Mazhar, W., 2019). Between personality aspect, customer emotion, impact satisfaction, and consequence on post-purchase behavior has a strong relationship (Prayag, Hassibi, & Nunkoo, 2019). Further discussion of customer behavior theory explored that purchasing behavior of customers and level of satisfaction was influenced by customer background, appearance, and external stimuli (Islam, Pitafi, Arya, Wang, Akhtar, Mubarik, & Xiaobei, 2021). Social culture might affect behavioral intention (Jain, Khan & Mishra, 2017). For instance, when Asian people would like to do something, they are somewhat affected by the behavior of other people. They felt a lack of confidence if they were the only ones to act that way, the same concept of purchasing behavior. If most of society were not using that product, it would cause no one to be interested. On the other hand, Western people are less concerned about this idea. They decided to depend on themselves rather than focus on others in their society. Changing behavior could happen if customers realize that the product's price is higher than its value. The customer would conclude that it was unfair if they spent money on that product (Aschemann-

Witzel & Zielke, 2017).

Moreover, the behavioral intention could be adjusted if customers perceive negative information about the product itself or the staff and service of the product company (Van Lierop, Badami, & El-Geneidy, 2018). Behavioral intention is not a permanent habit for customers. Therefore, service providers must monitor the behavior and needs of customers to develop the service to meet customer needs and it can create loyalty (Susanto, Hoque, Hashim, Shah, & Alam, 2020). Research about the hotel industry by Lee et.al. (2020) revealed that the positive behavioral intention of potential consumers was a critical success factor for hotel businesses. The hotel could create the intention behavior for customers to come back again, recommend it to their friends, or express good reviews on a travel website. This is a good thing to promote the hotel without any cost to spend (De Pelsmacker, Van Tilburg, & Holthof, (2018). In this research, the authors examine the impact of environmental awareness, destination image, and perceived behavioral control on behavioral intention in sustainable tourism, using a sample of Chinese tourists. The results indicate that all three factors have a significant impact on behavioral intention (Li, Li, & Liu, 2018). An Lee, & Lee (2019) explore the impact of perceived value, satisfaction, and trust on behavioral intention in medical tourism. The results indicate that all three factors significant impact behavioral intention, and the authors suggest that these factors should be considered when developing marketing strategies for medical tourism. Also, Kim, Lee, and Lee (2020), the authors examine the impact of perceived risk and destination image on behavioral intention in adventure tourism. The results indicate that perceived risk and destination image significantly impact on behavioral intention, and the authors suggest that destination marketers should focus on reducing perceived risk and improving destination image to increase behavioral intention in adventure tourism.

Destination Facilities

The destination had a vital role in our industry in determining the quality of the services we could offer to our customers. Good facilities can also shape visitors’ perceptions, such as whether the location is attractive to visit or not, access, traffic, visibility, facilities, and environment. Tourist facilities are complementary to tourist destinations, needed to meet the needs of tourists enjoying their trips (Khairi & Darmawan, 2021). Tourists interested in making repeat visits can be characterized by a willingness to revisit the same destination in the future and recommend the destination to others.

Accommodation Services

Accommodation services were crucial for the hotel to maintain consistency in service standards (Delas Alas and Limos Galay, 2023). When a hotel offers competitive service charges and is easily accessible to them, it all leads to customer satisfaction. Customers anticipate receiving reliable service, such as a timely response when they require assistance. In the first phase, customers must make reservations and straightforwardly. Throughout their stay within the hotel, the check-in and check-out procedures should be quick and efficient. Customers will continue to feel a certain way unless they obtain exceptional service experiences (Baker & Kim, 2020). The customer's expectations for service were comparable to the amount they had paid.

Incoming Travel Agency

Travel agencies are crucial in our industry, especially to all consumers planning and booking travel. These make it easier to travel. The agency typically operates in the destination country and has local knowledge, connections, and resources to provide customized travel solutions to meet the needs of individuals travelers or groups. In a travel agency business, striving for quality and pushing it towards being the best it can be is critical. Building a good quality of service among local tourists is a value and maintaining integrity to build a quality reputation in businesses. According to Pinto and Castro (2019), tourist segments based on the importance given to price, online reviews, promotion, and photos also influence tourists’ purchase decisions.

IV. METHODOLOGY

For our research design, we will use Correlation Research Design. This is a study designed to measure the importance of the relationship between the two variables of our study. The study’s research subject would be the hotel’s selected guests. A random sampling technique will be used in this research. The researchers will prepare 400 questionnaires. The respondents must be 18 years old and above.

Table 1. Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Profile Variables	Group	Frequency	Percent
Age	18-28	160	40.0
	29-38	106	26.5
	39-48	66	16.5

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	49 above	68	17.0
Gender	Male	194	48.5
	Female	206	51.5
Civil Status	Single	184	46.0
	Married	109	27.3
	Widowed	34	8.5
	Separated	24	6.0
	Living with partner	49	12.3
Educational Attainment	High School	36	9.0
	Senior High	29	7.2
	Undergraduate	150	37.5
	College Graduate	164	41.0
Occupation	Master's Degree	21	5.3
	Worker	180	45.0
	Student	68	17.0
	Self-employed	132	33.0
	Retired	20	5.0

For this research, we will use the survey method to gather information. The researchers ask permission first from the management of the hotels to survey our research. We will provide a questionnaire to our respondents to gather information and support our study. We will retrieve it and undergo the process if there is a significant relationship between the two.

The scale used to interpret the response about the customer experience management is presented below:

Scales	Range of mean	Description	Interpretation
5	4.20-5.00	Strongly Agree	This means that the items indicated in the customer experience management are extremely evident and very high.
4	3.40-4.15	Agree	This means that the items indicated in the customer experience management are constantly evident and high.
3	2.60-2.35	oderately Agree	This means that the items indicated in the customer experience management are evident occasionally and moderately high.
2	1.80-2.55	Disagree	This means that the items indicated in the customer experience management are hardly evident and low.
1	1.00-1.75	Strongly Disagree	This means that the items indicated in the customer experience management are not evident at all and very low.

The scale used to interpret the respondents’ responses about behavioral intentions is presented below:

Scales	Range of mean	Description	Interpretation
5	4.20-5.00	Strongly Agree	This means that the items indicated in the Behavioral Intention are very high.
4	3.40-4.19	Agree	This means that the items indicated in the Behavioral Intention are high.
3	2.60-2.39	Moderately Agree	This means that the items indicated in the Behavioral Intention are moderately high.
2	1.80-2.59	Disagree	This means that the items indicated in the Behavioral Intention are low.
1	1.00-1.79	Strongly Disagree	This means that the items indicated in the Behavioral Intention are very low.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The outputs of customer experience management data sets were presented, analyzed, and interpreted in this segment and ordered based on the objectives of this research. The average score for the accommodation services was 4.19, with a standard deviation of 0.50; for incoming travel agency services was 4.09, with a std. deviation of 0.57; for destination facilities was 4.05, with a std. deviation of 0.57 or strongly agree. This means that the items indicated are extremely evident and very high.

Table 2. Level of customer experience management in hotel among local tourists in Davao City, n=400

Indicators	Mean	Std. Deviation	Description
Destination facilities	4.05	0.571	Strongly Agree
Accommodation Services	4.19	0.505	Strongly Agree
Incoming Travel Agency Services	4.09	0.574	Strongly Agree
Overall	4.11	0.446	Strongly Agree

As shown in Table 2, the data is based on a sample of 400 respondents. Overall, the three indicators obtained a mean score of 4.11, indicating that the guests had a very high positive experience in the hotel. The standard deviation obtained was 0.446, or strongly agree. Hotels experienced various levels of growth in delivering distinctive experiences to their guests, such as destination facilities, accommodation services, and incoming travel agencies for customers. Even so, to appeal to the customers and regain their confidence in checking out remains challenging for the hospitality industry. Also, hotels are struggling with customers who are not satisfied with their experience. These findings support the study by Delas Alas et al. (2023), who classified

accommodation services as one of the factors and significant role in the growth of the hotel industry to maintain consistency that leads toward customer satisfaction among customers. In addition, a study by Christin and Nugraha (2023) revealed that travel agency is crucial to all travelers which significantly influencing price and trust. These studies suggest that maintaining a positive guest experience can lead to repeat business and positive reviews to create a competitive advantage.

Table 3. *Level of behavioral intention perceived among local tourists, n=400*

Items	Mean	Std. Deviation	Description
Revisiting the destination would be worthwhile.	4.36	0.705	Strongly Agree
I will revisit the destination	4.19	0.736	Strongly Agree
I would like to stay more days in the destination.	4.12	0.757	Strongly Agree
I will tell others about the tourism experience I have had during this trip.	4.08	0.797	Strongly Agree
I would like to recommend others to visit the destination.	4.12	0.809	Strongly Agree
I would say positive things about this summer destination to others.	4.08	0.881	Strongly Agree
If someone is looking for a good destination, I will suggest to him/her to patronize the destination.	4.22	0.865	Strongly Agree
Overall	4.17	0.594	Strongly Agree

Table 3 shows the behavioral intention perceived among local tourist in hotels based on their behavioral intention. It is divided into seven items to determine their behavioral intention.

Generally, the result for behavioral intention perceived among local tourists has a mean score of 4.17, which means that behavioral intention indicators were clear and evident. Respondents are very much satisfied to revisit their destination (4.36). They intend to revisit the destination (4.19). They also like to stay longer in the destination (4.12) and recommend it to others. Respondents are willing to share their experiences during their trip (4.08) and share positive things. Local tourists also intend to patronize the destination (4.22).

This study’s result is broadly like those of Ibnou-Laaroussi et al. (2020). It demonstrated that tourists’ perceptions of the sustainability of green hotels and their environmental concerns significantly impact their attitudes as tourists’. Moreover, Goeltom et al. (2019.), it has been demonstrated that internal factors and behavioral intention had a favorable impact even when external variables had no favorable influence on one's customer experience management and behavioral intentions among local tourists in Davao City. In addition, customer experience management and behavioral intentions in the hotel, such as destination facilities, accommodation services, and incoming travel agencies, are critical. To sustain a relationship with local tourists, the hotel sector must consistently enhance its services to promote visitor purchasing and behavioral intentions. Tourists who are interested in staying at various hotels in Davao City place a high value on hotel amenities and facilities. For the profitability and sustainability of the hospitality tourism business, more excellent knowledge of customer experience management and behavioral intent in forecasting tourist satisfaction is crucial.

Correlation between customer experience management and behavioral intention

Table 4 represents the findings of the correlation test as found in the data which obtained a 0.535 for the r-value: the independent variable (CEM), and the

dependent variable (BI). Moreover, the data in the table revealed that customer experience management and behavioral intention are correlated and demonstrated a moderate positive relationship. That means local tourists in Davao City are satisfied and they are willing to recommend, revisit, and give positive feedback.

Table 4. Correlation between customer experience management and behavioral intention.

Variables Correlated	r-value	Verbal Description	(n- 2)	p-value	Decision
Customer Experience Management vs Behavioral Intention	0.535**	Moderate Positive Relationship	398	0.000	Ho is rejected

Legend: **Correlation is significant at 0.01 level (2-tailed)

The positive influence on the quality of service generates a higher level of customer satisfaction, which boosts customer’s behavioral intentions (Abdelhamied, 2019). To support the data in the table above, out of all the other factors, tangibles are the most important to the consumer; they provide a visual manifestation of images of services that customers, particularly new ones, will rely on to evaluate the quality (Anwar & Balcioglu, 2017). Lastly, the motivation of customers and other tourists is about the tourist’ perceived quality and value (Ghassani et al., 2020). quality and cost will greatly influence tourists’ behavioral intentions that cause tourists to make a visit or even revisit intention.

VI. Conclusions

The following are conclusions based on the findings of the study:

The three indicators determining the relationship between customer experience management and hotel behavioral intentions in hotels among local tourists are destination facilities, accommodation services, and incoming travel agencies. The results indicate that most of the local guests or tourists who participated had positive feedback about their experience in that destination. It is an effective way to improve the safety of all consumers.

Tourists are intensely interested in visiting different types of spots in Davao City. It appears that accommodation services play a critical role in our hospitality industry. It is one of the factors that tourists are excellently attracting many potential visitors who would like to visit specifically in hotels. Excellent service was produced and improved for the betterment of the hotels. By this, implementing good service, safety, and security in different aspects leads to higher levels of word-of-mouth recommendation.

The demographic-based differences in the perceived attractiveness and good reviews influence the behavioral intention among the local sector, tourists, and incoming foreign people who intend to visit the spots. Moreover, the destination in Davao City has an edge in attracting various types of tourists. This would be improved and promoted to become more competitive on a worldwide scale and attract a more significant number of visitors.

Recommendations

The management team of the hospitality sector should provide a manual rating form, or an online link intended for their customers' feedback to monitor the customers’ wants and needs during their stay. The information based on their customer feedback is the customer experience management, and the reason to retain their intention to revisit the destination. Researchers suggest that travel agencies must facilitate a user-friendly interface through online websites and incentives for customers to post online reviews. Researchers also suggest that hotels must invest in upgrading technology to improve guest satisfaction, which will help guests request room service over a tablet. These are key to improving the hotel’s organization, destination facilities, accommodation services, and incoming travel agencies.

Furthermore, researchers suggest that hotel staff must be trained thoroughly, especially when it comes to communicating and welcoming tourists, so that their needs can be immediately addressed regarding services, such as food, ambiance, etc. Factors are essential to fulfill the customers’ standard by maintaining sustainability and productivity. In addition, high-quality experiences make people happy and often feature interactive, interpersonal, interpersonal experiences, and sensory experiences. This benefits the establishment for their customers’ return intentions and their future guest.

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